

D6.4: Competition Awards

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1 Executive Summary

LoCloud is a Best Practice Network co-funded under the [CIP ICT-PSP Programme](#) of the European Commission. One of the main goals of the project has been to add a significant amount of content from small and medium sized cultural institutions to Europeana¹.

Europeana provides access to millions of digitised materials from European museums, libraries, archives and multimedia collections via its portal. LoCloud has had a specific focus on the content available in smaller cultural institutions partly because their content has been under-represented in Europeana but also for its focus on the local cultural heritage.

LoCloud organised an open competition during 2015 with the dual aim of stimulating innovative use of cloud technologies and the creation of views of local places using content made available via Europeana. The year began with a Hackathon hosted at the Google Culture Institute in Paris. The launch of the “My Local Heritage” and “My LoCloud Services” strands of the competition followed in early summer 2015. The competition resulted in some interesting and enjoyable presentations of local heritage seen through the eyes of students and others. The competition concluded with a prize award ceremony held at LoCloud’s final conference in Amersfoort.

This deliverable describes the LoCloud competition and the related dissemination activities. Through the competition it was possible to reach stakeholders outside the partner organizations, like students, librarians, journalists, designer and others working in the cultural field.

The entries to the LoCloud competition can be viewed on the project website at:

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition>.

¹ <http://www.europeana.eu>

2 Introduction

The aim of the LoCloud competition was to stimulate best practice and innovation among individual regions and localities in a 'view' in Europeana of the history and heritage of their locality.

Another goal of the competition was to contribute to dissemination about the project and its results across Europe to curators, local historians, students, volunteers, developers, aggregators and cultural institutions.

The LoCloud Competition was organized in 2 rounds:

- 1) LoCloud Hackathon, held in Paris in February 2015
- 2) LoCloud Competition, launched in May 2015 with 2 strands :
 - My Local Heritage
 - My LoCloud Services

The competition was been promoted through LoCloud's web site, LoCloud partner's websites, Facebook and Twitter.

Dedicated webpages were set up for both the Hackathon and the LoCloud Competition:

- The Hackathon micro-site provided developers with access information about LoCloud Services and Europeana content, and the Hackathon itself: <http://more.LoCloud.eu/hackathon/>.
- A new section was created within LoCloud's Website for the competition providing information for potential participants about the two strands, the kind of entries that we were looking for and an application form: <http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information>.

LoCloud partners created dedicated web pages in their national languages and translated the competition press release to launch the competition in their country. Partners actively promoted the competition through their networks. Details and the links of the national web pages are published at <http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/In-your-country>.

Thirty-seven entries were received for the LoCloud Competition and five teams participated in the LoCloud Hackathon.

The entries to the Hackathon were judged and the prize awarded to the winner on the day of the Hackathon. The entries to the LoCloud Competition were judged in November 2015 and the winners invited to present their entries and receive their prize at the LoCloud final event, in Amersfoort, Netherlands on 5th February 2016.

All of the competition entries were published on the LoCloud website and entrants received a Certificate of Participation in appreciation for their contributions.

3 LoCloud Hackathon, Paris

EuropeanaTech is a community of experts, developers and researchers from the R&D sector, which forms part of the Europeana Network. Europeana organised the second international EuropeanaTech conference at the Bibliothèque nationale de France in Paris in February 2015. LoCloud was invited by Europeana to organise a Hackathon in a collaboration with the Google Culture Institute in Paris as part of this event.

The Hackathon was organised by the Digital Curation Unit of the Athena Research Centre on behalf of LoCloud as part of the competition.

The aim of the Hackathon was to invite developers to try out some of the services that have been created by LoCloud and to use them to come up with some innovative applications.

The LoCloud Hackathon was held on February 11, 2015 at the Google Culture Institute in Paris.

3.1 Call for participation

The call for participation was launched by Athena RC, who set up a micro-site for developers to access information about the Hackathon:

<http://more.LoCloud.eu/hackathon/>.

The call invited developers to take part in a Hackathon at the Google Cultural Institute in Paris on Wednesday, February 11th, to build an innovative application using LoCloud Services and Europeana data.

The call was advertised via the EuropeanaTech mailing list, a news item on the LoCloud website and via social media.

3.2 The event

The Hackathon took place in the Lab at the Google Cultural Institute in Paris. After a short welcome to the Lab from Google and a presentation about LoCloud services, the participant's workstations were set up.

LoCloud services were made available for developers on Virtual Machines via the MORE infrastructure, including:

- The MORE repository itself,
- The Enrichment services,
- Geolocation services,
- Historical place names service,
- Vocabulary services and
- The Wikimedia application.

Sample Europeana content was also made available for download and through REST endpoints. Other useful information (such as thesauri) were also provided through REST.

APIs were available for the MoRe aggregator and the LoCloud micro-services for developers to use to build their own applications. The APIs were REST based and made use of one of the three following formats: XML, RDF, JSON.

All participants were asked to bring their own laptops and to be familiar with the technologies used by the various services. Developers were invited to:

- create their own applications (e.g. a web based app or a mobile app) or
- create their own metadata enrichment services in any programming language through MORE's virtual enrichment driver (VED) and plug them in directly into the enrichment process.

Figure 1: Hackathon in progress in the Lab at the Google Culture Institute

The developers were working in an amazing space. The Google Lab has a gigapixel display wall, which in the later part of the day was used to display some of the results of the Institute's very high definition scanning of artworks.

3.3 Presentation of the applications

The five teams participating to the LoCloud Hackathon came up with some interesting ideas and applications in a short space of time. All 5 teams presented their prototype applications to the panel of judges and the other participants at the end of the day.

The applications presented were very varied. Two teams came up with map-based applications for end-users – one for crowd-sourcing the addition of map locations to archives of photos and the other a route planning app for tourists. A third team proposed creating links between archive items and news from cultural institutions. The final two applications were designed to help with managing the

process of ingestion – one to quality check metadata and the other to help project managers to monitor the progress of people working in the system.

An international judging panel was appointed to review all the entries to the Hackathon and to select the winner. The panel included:

Costis Dallas (Athena Research Centre and University of Toronto),

James Helmsley (Europeana),

Andy Neal (Digital New Zealand),

Ingrida Vosylute (University of Vilnius) and

Kate Fernie (2Culture).

Figure 2: Kate Fernie congratulating the developers who took part in the LoCloud hackathon

The panel voted for the most innovative application/service presented at the Hackathon.

3.4 The winner

The winning entry was **MoRe Quality** presented by Vangelis Banos.

The [winning application](#) was developed with the aim of making it possible to check the quality of metadata in a repository and make corrections. The application uses the LoCloud MoRe API key to check for common metadata problems (such as invalid date formats, author names, language codes) and to make corrections to normalize the data. The application is configurable in a way that allows repository managers to design additional checks.

Figure 3: Vangelis Banos, the winner of the hackathon

The winner of the competition was awarded with a prize of a Moto 360 smartwatch .

The concept

The Metadata & Object Repository (MoRe²) is an easy and powerful tool to aggregate information and harvest metadata from multiple sources in multiple schemas. The

² <http://more.dcu.gr/>

variety of aggregated metadata usually creates problematic situations regarding the quality of the harvested metadata.

Metadata may pass the standard Europeana XML validity tests but elements may include problematic values. For instance: a dc:date value or an author name could be formatted in the wrong way or be incomplete. The aim of the MoRe Quality tool is to implement a validation system, which could be able to catch these errors and produce useful reports to the collection administrators.

MoRe Quality communicates with the LoCloud MoRe instance using a specific user API Key, retrieves the ingested metadata and performs evaluations to identify common errors such as:

- Invalid date formats
- Invalid author names
- Invalid hyperlinks
- Invalid language codes

The application is implemented in such a way that enables developers to add extra evaluation rules in an easy and intuitive way by implementing simple functions - plugins.

The full source code for the application has been made freely available at:
<https://bitbucket.org/vbanos/more-quality/>

The screenshot shows the Bitbucket repository page for 'MoRe Quality - Metadata evaluation tool prototype'. The page is divided into a left sidebar and a main content area. The sidebar includes a profile picture of Vangelis Banos, the repository name, and navigation options like 'Clone', 'Compare', 'Fork', 'Overview', 'Source', 'Commits', 'Branches', 'Pull requests', and 'Downloads'. The main content area contains the following sections:

- MoRe Quality - Metadata evaluation tool prototype**: This application won the first prize at the LoCloud Hackathon which was conducted on the 11th of February 2015 at the premises of the Google Cultural Ins. The author is Vangelis Banos who is working with Future Library from Greece.
- Concept**: A lot of people are using the MoRe aggregator to gather metadata and publish them to Europeana. The problem is that the ingested metadata are not valid. Metadata may pass the standard Europeana XML structure tests but they may include problematic metadata values. For instance, a dc:date value could be century<dc:date> or an author name may be something like this: <dc:creator>Mike</dc:creator>. The aim of the MoRe quality tool is to implement a validation system which could be able to catch these errors and produce useful reports to the collection.
- Features**: MoRe Quality communicates with the LoCloud MoRe repository using a specific user API Key, retrieves the ingested metadata and performs evaluations to date formats (ISO 8601 standard) Invalid hyperlinks Invalid language codes (ISO 639 standard) Invalid author names
- Technology**: MoRe Quality is implemented using python 2.7. The following python modules are used: Virtual environments Flask Python Requests BeautifulSoup4 pyco modules is included in the source code in the requirements.txt file.
- Future Work**:
 - New validation rules could be implemented using standard python functions.
 - The system can become configurable, enabling the user to select the rules she/he would like to apply to each metadata element.
 - The system could send feedback to the MoRe aggregator with technical metadata regarding the identified issues. Dear MoRe developers, please m
 - Performance

Figure 4: MoRe Quality application

4 LoCloud competition

The main aim of the LoCloud international competition was to encourage people to explore a favourite place or part of their local history through Europeana, and present their experience online in the form of web pages, a blog or video. A second strand was included to encourage uses of LoCloud Services.

The competition strands were:

- 1) **"My Local Heritage"** for curators, volunteers, local historians, or students to present their experience of exploring their local heritage in Europeana in a short video, blog post or online essay.
- 2) **"My LoCloud Services"** for developers, aggregators and cultural institutions to present their implementation or development of LoCloud services.

The competition was launched in May 2015 with the initial deadline for entries given as the 1st of October. The deadline was later extended to the 8th of November, with the aim of encouraging more schools to participate (the 1st deadline was felt to be too early).

The competition entries were judged at the end of November 2015 and the winners announced. The winners were invited to present their entries at the LoCloud final event, which was held in Amersfoort, in the Netherlands on 5th February 2016.

The competition winners received a prize consisting in a tablet and a diploma.

4.1 The launch of the LoCloud competition

LoCloud competition was launched on the 13th of May 2015 with a new webpage and a press release.

A section of the LoCloud website was created for the competition. This provided information about the competition, the types of entries that we were looking for in each strand, links to pages about the competition in each country and a link to the application form.

Figure 5: Competition pages in the LoCloud website

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information>

Project partners translated the press release into their national language, and most also created a webpage in their own language to promote the LoCloud competition. As a result the competition pages were available in 21 Languages (including English).

All LoCloud partners publicized the competition among their national networks, through their websites, social media, national events and direct mailing.

A link was created from the competition section of the LoCloud website to the pages created by the partners in their national language. This page is available at: <http://www.LoCloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information/In-your-country>

In your country

Please select from the list below for information about the competition in your own language. If a competition page is not listed for your country please feel free to email the listed contact.

Country	Contact	Competition webpage
Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology	
Denmark	Kulturstyrelsen	
Greece	Athena Research and Innovation Centre in Information Communication & Knowledge Technologies	
Iceland	Minjastofnun Íslands /The Cultural Heritage Agency of Iceland	
Ireland	The Discovery Programme	
Poland	Instytut Chemii Bioorganicznej PAN	

Figure 6: List of the country pages for the LoCloud competition

The competition was promoted through social media (mainly via Twitter), through events (such as the LoCloud workshop at the Digital Heritage conference in Granada) and a Press release.

A press release was published on LoCloud’s website in English and this was then translated into different languages by the majority of LoCloud partners. The aim was to attract creative people across Europe, with different backgrounds and develop an innovative product celebrating local history.

Press release

Participate in the LoCloud international competition to celebrate local history!

Are you a creative person?
 Are you interested in your local history?
 Would you like to explore your creativity and develop something new?
 Would you like to share it across Europe?
 LoCloud’s competition could be for you!
 LoCloud is launching an international competition focusing on local heritage and culture. The competition has two categories:
 1) **My Local Heritage**: encourages people to explore a favorite place or part of their local history through the online resources in Europeana, and to present their experience online through web pages, a blog or even a video. The video should be no longer than 5-8 minutes. (See for example this video <http://vimeo.com/52802290>)
 2) **My LoCloud Services**: is for developers, aggregators and individual cultural institutions to showcase their use of the many services developed as part of LoCloud. For information about the services: <http://support.locloud.eu/>
 The deadline for the entries is 1st October 2015.
 Competition winners will be announced at the LoCloud final event, which will be held in Amersfoort, Netherlands on 5th February 2016. Accommodation and travel costs will be covered by LoCloud for up to 2 people for each winning entry.
 A prize of a tablet computer or smart watch will be presented to the winners and runners up of each category. Winning entries will be publicized by LoCloud and Europeana.
 Gunnar Urtegaard, from the National Archives of Norway (project coordinator) says:
 "I think cloud based services and infrastructure for the heritage sector are the future.
 Such services will help institutions to offer better services and more high quality content to user all over Europe. I invite you

Figure 7: The press release for the LoCloud competition published on the project website (left), MECD’s website (below left) and the National Archives of Norway’s website (below right)

4.2 Procedure for selecting the winners

Thirty-seven entries were submitted to the My Local Heritage strand of the competition. An international judging panel reviewed these entries and the winner and runner up were selected.

4.2.1 The judging panel

An international selection committee was appointed to review all the entries and to select the winners of the LoCloud competition. The committee included:

- Vilde Ronge, National Archives of Norway, assistant director
- Milena Popova, Europeana, Business Development Manager Re-use Services
- Kate Fernie, 2Culture Associates, project manager LoCloud

4.2.2 Criteria

For My local heritage the jury made the selections following these main criteria:

1. First looking for how the person/team has explored their local history or favourite place using Europeana.
2. Second observing if the entry included simple text or spoken word kept simple so that the entries could be shared with people from across Europe
3. Third verifying if the entry shared the experience of using Europeana in some way
4. Fourth checking if the licence for the content used in the entries was openly licenced, or the rights cleared by contacting the institution that provided the content.

Each jury member viewed and explored each of the entries over a period of two weeks.

A free online tool called “Trello” was used to support the judging process. The competition entries were mounted as cards in a Trello project.

Figure 8: LoCloud competition entries in Trello

By clicking on a card it was possible to open it and view the information supplied by the participants on their entry form. In cases where the entrant had provided the description of their entry in the local language, the text was been translated using Google Translate and added to the card as an aid for he judging panel.

Figure 9: Competition entry card in Trello

Each card included a link to the entry, in cases where the entry was submitted as a video posted on YouTube the embedded viewer enabled viewing within Trello itself. Several of the entries were in the form of blogposts, webpages and videos posted in Vimeo; links were provided to these outside Trello.

Figure 10: Viewing the video entry card within Trello

The card enabled voting and included a comment box for judges.

Each judge looked at all of the entries and used Trello to vote for their short-list and to comment on the entries.

The judging panel then met via Skype to discuss the short-listed entries and choose the winner and the runner up.

4.3 Participants

Most of the entries resulted in a creative remix of Europeana content, creating a blog, a video or a website.

There were thirty-seven entries from fourteen different countries. The majority of entrants were students; there were also several librarians and people working in cultural institutions, designers, a journalist and a music composer. Most of the entries were videos; there were also websites, blogs and some other resources.

To show the variety of entry types there are some examples listed in the table below:

Country	Title	Description
Bulgaria	Explore your local history through Europeana	The video starts with a librarian, scanning photos for the Europeana website. Then continues with a girl, who visits the Public library in Varna, searches for photos of her town in the Europeana website and then discovers the real photos in the library. She explores her home-town and sees the difference through the years.
Ireland	Culture & Heritage in County Meath	MeathHeritage.com is a dynamic public facing website which gives users access to information pertaining to over 3000 National Monuments in County Meath. The website consolidates information from a number of Open Data projects including the National Monuments Service, The Logainm Placename Project, Geograph UK & Ireland and Europeana. The website is a searchable by over 300 monument classifications and 800 townlands. It promotes community engagement by allowing members of the public to contribute information by posting reviews, comments, information and photos about each of the National Monuments.
Hungary	This Place is COOL!	This Place is COOL! project is an interactive city history based mapping system of Hungarian noppa design group. The various elements of this city-scale installation come together to form a map which marks various places in Budapest with interesting histories, sites which we don't really notice during the hustle and bustle of our everyday lives. The goal of the project was to point out man-made places of interest which are usually hidden from our view, either metaphorically or physically, by buildings, other objects or time itself. They can be houses which have gained new functions, or city squares, street corners, stores or even natural treasures that have literary or cultural-historical significance.
Croatia	AZ - Croatian Glagolitic Murals	A video about the Glagolitic script, as well as Glagolitic tradition, is a Croatian cultural phenomenon unique for its linguistic, graphic, ethnological, anthropological and semiotic characteristics. In 2014, following the decision of the Ministry of Culture, the Glagolitic script was inscribed into the list of intangible cultural heritage of the Republic of Croatia.
Serbia	Kraljevo in Motion	Video presentation in time lapse called "Kraljevo in Motion". The idea of this presentation is to present Kraljevo and the life in it in 24 hours.
Serbia	Greetings from Despotovac - Pozdrav iz Despotovca	Video presenting the local history of the town of Despotovac with significant emphasis on Manasija monastery, which is located near the city. As the one of the sites of world cultural heritage, Manasia is deeply imbued into the past of the town which is named by monastery founder, despot Stefan Lazarevic.

Country	Title	Description
Spain	Time limitation	Blog made by a time traveller, who in every post talks about a stage of the Zaragoza's history. The first post is a presentation about the traveller, and since the second post he starts the trips, until he develops some addiction to the trips.
Spain	Cathedral of our lady of the Pilar	Blog combining different work programs which contain video, photographs, presentations. Much of the information has been obtained from different websites. The main goal was to share with other internet users, information about a part of the city, Zaragoza.
Spain	Monuments of Zaragoza	Video about the most important monuments of Zaragoza telling the history of each one.
Serbia	The sights of Oreskovica	Interactive image about sights of Oreskovica, a small village in eastern Serbia. Students of Primary school "Djura Jaksic" Oreskovica (3rd grade students) created this image with help of their teacher to present to their peers from other countries, which are the most important sights of their place. Students chose 6 sights (The Regional Center for Protection of Hail, The Church of Saint Great-martyr Marina, The Memorial Fountain, The Hunting Lodge, Primary school "Djura Jaksic" and The Cultural Center). They made photo for each sight and wrote a short text. They uploaded their materials on Internet and created the interactive image, by using Thinglink.
Spain	Z Confidential	Short film telling a detective story. The young detectives follow trails conducting to a big discovery. It's a mystery about the Nobel laureate Ramón y Cajal, about his investigation and the modern city.
Bulgaria	Varna Beneath My Shoes	The idea of this video is to show how culturally rich any place could be, and especially Varna. Europeana helped to wake up curiosity and the video shows some girls walking down tiny little streets with mighty buildings discovering history with help of Europeana.
Italy	Mein Freund-Kamerad/Il mio nemico-amico	Video of two soldiers from different regiments are face to face in the Alps during the first World War. The students tried to imagine how their dialogue would be. On one side they behave like friends and help each other to tackle the winter on the mountains, sharing food on the other hand they know that on the next days maybe they will have to act like enemies in the next battle.
UK	A Glimpse of Victorian York	Video using visual and audio material from Europeana, York Museums Trust, Wikimedia and Freesound.org to explore the city of York. give depth and breadth. The viewer is guided round Victorian York by a couple, visiting key locations that tell a variety of different stories associated with the social, economic and industrial history of the city. The approach is highly visual with text kept short to cater for ESL viewers.
Slovenia	Europeana - knowledge in your hands	Video shows the use of Europeana in discovering local cultural heritage. A student has to write an essay about the city of Koper. She finds all the answers in Europeana.
Romania	A flash back in history	Short video to encourage people to access Europeana in order to discover their local history.
Romania	A walk in ... time	The video "A walk in ... time" invites the viewers to a short online walk in the park, the Central Park of Cluj-Napoca, but also to a walk in time, with the help of Europeana.
Denmark	Copenhagen - Do you know your local history?	The video shows how to use Europeana in collaboration with the library to explore one's local history. Both contain large amounts of data on our heritage both physically and digitally. Europeana is available to us in the urban space and allows us to further explore our local heritage even when we are on the move.

Country	Title	Description
Denmark	Time has told me	Video telling the story of Copenhagen's harbour through the eyes of an artist. The reminiscence from the old days is still here - and so are the stories. Though it's only 10 min from Copenhagen centre, it feels like stepping into a different world; It's rough and mild at the same time. The author of this video composed the music accompanying the video .

4.4 Competition entries

The table below shows all LoCloud competition's entries with title, name of the participants and provenance. All of the competition entries can be viewed at:

<http://locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition>

Country	Title	Name of author/s	Institution (if applicable)
Bulgaria	Explore your local history through Europeana	Aneliya Kalcheva	Robert Gordon University Scotland
Ireland	Culture & Heritage in County Meath	Alison Boland	National University of Ireland
Ireland	Glascarraig Motte and Bailey Historical and Archaeological Survey	Byron Jones	Rubicon Heritage Ireland
Hungary	This Place is COOL!	ALVÉGI Lóci, EKE Tamás, VARGA Lívía, KOVÁCS Andrea	Noppa design
Serbia	Uncle Isa's School	Dejan Kreculj	Public School 'Jovan Jovanovic Zmaj', Kovin
Croatia	AZ - Croatian Glagolitic Murals	Jasna Horvat, Domagoj Topić, Josipa Mijoč, Sanda Katavić-Čaušić	Institute for Scientific and Art Research in Creative Industries – Andizet
Croatia	"This is my Cultural Heritage": Old Postcards Framework Printed by 3D Printer and Inspired by Europeana	Filip Cvitić, Nikola Ugarković	Graphic designer, Student
Serbia	Echoes of Memories	Mirko Drmanac	Public Library "Vladislav Petković Dis" Čačak
Serbia	Kraljevo in Motion	Zlatko Milojicic	Faculty of Electronic Engineering
Serbia	Greetings from Despotovac - Pozdrav iz Despotovca	Tomislav Marković	Department of History, the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Spain	Time limitation	Lucas Blaquez Teixeira Daniel Gracia Alevesque Alba Montañés Aguilar Marina Asín Soro	Goya Secondary School
Spain	Cathedral of our lady of the Pilar	Marta Soria Gracia, Marina Castellano Aznar, Lara Hurtado Sieso, Marina del Olmo Jalle, Elena Calderón Aznar	Goya Secondary School
Spain	Sites of Zaragoza	Rebeca Pérez Duato, Raquel Gadea Gotor,	Goya Secondary School

Country	Title	Name of author/s	Institution (if applicable)
		Elena Cegoñino Giral, Fernanda Díaz Neira, Marta García Robles	
Spain	Monuments of Zaragoza	Irene Marín Guallar, María Busons Herrera, Blanca Illana Rangel, Sara Rodrigo Jiménez,	Goya Secondary School
Spain	Monuments of Zaragoza	Irene Marín Guallar, María Busons Herrera, Blanca Illana Rangel, Sara Rodrigo Jiménez,	Goya Secondary School
Serbia	The sights of Oreskovica	Slavica Gomilanovic (teacher-mentor), team of students: Jelena Petrovic, Danilo Strajinovic, Sara Dimitrijevic, Tamara Paunovic, Anita Markovic	Primary school "Djura Jaksic" Oreskovica
Serbia	Moj grad Kraljevo	Gordana Petrović	Mašinska tehnička škola "14.oktobar" Kraljevo
Spain	Z Confidential	Andrea Samsón, Sergio Gracia Bolea, Ignacio José Lambán Sánchez, Gloria Martínez Gómez, Paula Barzu,	Goya Secondary School
Bulgaria	Varna Beneath My Shoes	Marina Stoilova, Kosara Bakalova	Secondary School Varna
Spain	Los viajes de Santiago	Maria Rocio Moreiras Plaza	Interdepartmental library of the University of Santiago de Compostela
Lithuania	Europeana - virtual to reality	Greta Alksnytė, Aistė Čiučiurkaitė	University of Vilnius
Italy	Mein Freund- Kamerad/Il mio nemico- amico	Nadine Pescoller, Nora Planatscher, Angelica Schanung and Hannah Spechtenhauser	Secondary School of languages
Italy	Reading the past...	Jennifer Comploi, Anna Costamoling, Debora Dellosto and Ismahan Ouerghi	Secondary School of languages
England, U.K	A Glimpse of Victorian York	Izzy Bartley	University of York
Slovenia	Europeana - knowledge in your hands	Tina Škrokov and Urška Bonin	Srečko Vilhar Public Library, Koper
Slovenia	Maribor in the past and today	Mihael Muršec, Sven Pušnik, Patrik Rek, Nejc-Filip Svenšek.	II. High school Maribor
Spain	Catedral de Zamora	Blanca Flor Herrero Morán, César Amador Isidro García	Art-History Department - Univeristy of Salamanca
Spain	Leyendo en mis rincones favoritos de Barañain	Jesús Arana y Clara Flamarique	Biblioteca de Barañain
Romania	The Extraordinary Adventures of Private	Bogdan Stanciu	Sinteza monthly magazine, online version

Country	Title	Name of author/s	Institution (if applicable)
	Nistor		
Romania	A flash back in history	Catalin Cistelican	Secondary School, Cluj
România	Moşteirea mea locală: Mediaş	Ioana Teodora Duma	Biblioteca Municipală „St. L. Roth” Mediaş
Romania/România	Cluj and Its Monuments/ Cluj și monumentele sale	Paul-Daniel Golban	Universitatea Babeş-Bolyai Facultatea de Litere NO-EN Anul I / Babeş-Bolyai University Faculty of Letters NO-EN First Year
Romania	Rediscovering Cluj	Craciun Anamaria	
Romania	A walk in ... time	Stefan Mihai Tapastau	"Babes-Bolyai" University, The Faculty of Letters.
Romania	Europeana@Pinterest by Delia Chira	Chira Delia	"Octavian Goga" Cluj County Library
Romania	Let's make them aware	Baciu Diana-Laura	Biblioteca Judeteana "Octavian Goga" Cluj-Napoca
Denmark	Copenhagen - Do you know your local history?	Anna Cecilie Björklund and Trine Christensen	IT University
Denmark	Time has told me	Gunhild Øibakken Pedersen	Artist and musician

4.5 The winners of LoCloud competition

The winners of the My Local Heritage competition were as follows.

4.6 The winner

Figure 11: “Maribor in the past and today”

The winning entry was the video “Maribor in the past and today”. The video was produced by Mihael Muršec (a second grade high school student) with members of the school computer club from II High school, Maribor: Sven Pušnik, Patrik Rek, Nejc-Filip Svenšek.

“I've been interested on multimedia since the primary school” says Mihael Muršec.

The jury’s motivation

Mihael Muršec's video is a lively exploration of the town of Maribor then and now. There's a nice mixture of modern images and videos, with the inclusion of screen captures of searches on Europeana showing how the archives were discovered. The video shows how the town has changed and also how some aspects of people's lives continue from the past to today. The final sequence compares footage of modern sports/adventure activities to archive images of skiing and other sports about the town giving a strong impression of life in the town then and now.

4.7 The runner up

The runner up was "The Extraordinary Adventures of Private Nistor" by Bogdan Stanciu an experienced, award-winning journalist and non-fiction author based in Cluj-Napoca in Romania. The blog shows the story of a Romanian artilleryman in the Great War, who came to fight against the Japanese, for defending a German colony in nowadays China.

Figure 11: The extraordinary adventures of Private Nistor

Figure 12: Private Nistor's diary

Private Nistor sailed half the seas of the world to arrive in the Far East, aboard an Austro-Hungarian cruiser. He took part in the first battles recorded in history between a plane and a boat; he was taken prisoner by the Japanese and wrote a diary with all his adventures.

Private Nistor took part in the first battles between a plane and a boat, was taken prisoner by the Japanese and wrote a diary with all his adventures, which is now available online. The blog-post uses and cites Europeana as a primary source for text and photos, completing the story with views expressed by various historians and warfare experts.

4.8 Awards ceremony

The two winners were invited to Amersfoort for LoCloud's final Conference. The awards ceremony took place in the afternoon session. The competition awards were introduced by Kate Fernie who presented of a video showcase of the entries.

The showcase can be viewed at:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u5DNK-II_dw

LoCloud
Competition entries
Showcase

Henk Alkemade from RCE Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed presented the prizes to the winner and the runner up of the My Local Heritage competition. Both were awarded with a diploma and a tablet by, LoCloud partner as their prize.

Figure 13: Henk Alkemade presenting certificates to the competition winners Mihael Muršec (left) and Bogdan Stanciu (right)

Figure 14: Competition Certificate

5 LoCloud competition’s contribution to dissemination

Both the LoCloud project and Europeana were disseminated across Europe through the LoCloud competition, which provided a way of reaching out to curators, local historians, students, volunteers, developers, aggregators and cultural institutions.

The use of Google analytics on the project website enabled an overview of the page views generated by the LoCloud competition

A *page view* is defined as a view of a page on your site that is being tracked by the Analytics tracking code. If a user clicks reload after reaching the page, this is counted as an additional page view. If a user navigates to a different page and then returns to the original page, a second page view is recorded as well.

A *unique page view*, as seen in the *Content Overview* report, aggregates page views that are generated by the same user during the same session. A *unique page view* represents the number of sessions during which that page was viewed one or more times.

Competition Information Page

This page provided a brief introduction with links to the two strands of the competition ‘My Local Heritage’ and ‘My Local Services’ from the launch on 13th May 2015 to 11th January 2016.

The page received 1,912 page views of which 1,578 were unique.

Referrals

From the launch of the project up until the deadline there were 464 sessions from 53 referral sources. The top referrals to this page of the website were as follows:

- 132 (28,4%) from Facebook
- 49 (10.6%) from Vilnius University Faculty of Communication, Lithuania (kf.vu.lt) and
- 48 (10.3%) from Twitter.

There were also direct referrals to the two different stands of the project, which bypassed the competition introduction page.

My Local Heritage Referrals

The majority of 265 referrals to the “My Local Heritage” page came from Facebook with 61 page views (23%), followed by Twitter, 47 page views (17.7%) and 32 page views (12.1%) from netokracija.com.

My LoCloud Services Referrals

For the MyLoCloud Services strand of the competition pro.europeana.eu provided the highest number of referrals at 20 page views (13.2%), followed by Twitter, 13 page views (8.6%) and On the Move, the Cultural Mobility Information Network, 10 page views (6.6%).

My Local Heritage

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information/My-Local-Heritage>

Prior to the deadline date (8 Nov 2015) for submission of competition entries there were 1,283 page views of the "My Local Heritage" strand of the competition, 1,027 of

these were unique visitors and it ranks as sixth overall all in page views on LoCloud since the start of the project,

Visitors came from 47 countries; Serbia had the most visits at 236 (18.2%) followed by United Kingdom 198 (15.2%), Croatia 146 (11.2%) and Spain 116 (8.9%).

The page continued to receive visits after the deadline date. As of 24 February 2016 an additional 237 page views were reported with visits from 22 countries.

This page ranked as seventh of the pages viewed on the website since the start of the project.

My LoCloud Services

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information/My-LoCloud-Services>

There were 323 page views during the period of the competition with 275 unique visits. There have been a further 24 page views since the close of the competition.

Visitors to the page came from 39 countries, Spain and the United Kingdom shared the top viewed pages with 41 (12.7%)

Competition Press Release

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information/Press-release>

Prior to the competition deadline the press release was viewed 176 times of which 153 were unique views, visitors came from 29 countries with the United Kingdom with the most views (25) followed by Romania (23), Italy (17), Spain (15) and Ireland (11).

In Your Country Page

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information/In-your-country>

Project partners promoted the LoCloud Competition on their own websites in their local languages. The LoCloud “in-your-country” page provided links to these websites along with a dedicated contact for each country. There were 82 page views from 76 visitors to the “In Your Country” page.

Competition Entries

<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition>

On 11th January 2016 the competition pages were restructured to showcase all of the competition entries in preparation for the LoCloud Conference on 5 February 2016 in Amersfoort, Netherlands.

The collage shows a grid of 18 small entry thumbnails, each with a title and a small image. The entries are categorized by country: Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, and Romania. The detailed view on the right shows the LoCloud website interface for the entry 'Maribor in the past and today'. It features a video player with the title 'MOJA LOKALNA KULTURNA PEDIŠČINA' and a list of metadata including institution, country, short description, author, and short biography.

Upon completion of the judging process and announcement of the winners, all of the competition entries were made live on the LoCloud website and promoted through social media. Information relating to the competition entry requirements was moved to a sub menu.

To date this page received 342 page views. Visitors have come from 26 countries with Serbia, Romania, Spain, Croatia and Slovenia heading the list.

6 Conclusions

The LoCloud Competition ran in the final phase of the project was organized in two rounds: the LoCloud Hackathon held in Paris and LoCloud Competition divided in two strands “My Local Heritage” and My “LoCloud Services”.

The aim of the competition was to stimulate best practice and innovation among individual regions and localities in a ‘view’ in Europeana of the history and heritage of their locality, with awards to be presented at the Final Event.

A total of thirty-seven entries were received for the “My Local Heritage” competition. Five teams participated in the LoCloud Hackathon. There were no entries to the “My LoCloud Services” strand of the competition. Although there have been significant uses of LoCloud technology, the feedback that we received suggested that the prize was not sufficient to encourage entries from developers who preferred the Hackathon environment.

An important goal of the competition was to contribute towards disseminating the project across Europe and to raising awareness of Europeana amongst curators, local historians, students, volunteers, developers, aggregators and cultural institutions. All partners contributed to active dissemination of the competition through LoCloud’s web site, LoCloud partner’s websites, Facebook, Twitter, in conferences and other events.

The outcomes of the competition include an innovative application for quality assuring metadata and a series of highly enjoyable explorations of the local heritage created by Europeana end-users.

7 References

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